

Numerical Model for 6 Degrees of Freedom Dynamics of Offshore Floating Wind Turbines: A Code-to-Code Comparison between OpenFAST and MOST

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ABSTRACT: This paper introduces the latest MOST (Matlab-Simulink Offshore Simulation Tool), a novel nonlinear, time-domain numerical model designed specifically for simulating offshore floating wind turbines. MOST offers a comprehensive framework for accurately assessing platform dynamics in six degrees of freedom, predicting power production, and analyzing blade load cycles. Leveraging blade element momentum (BEM) theory for aerodynamics and WEC-Sim for hydrodynamics, MOST ensures robust simulation capabilities crucial for offshore renewable energy projects. Moreover, the integration with Matlab facilitates advanced control system analysis, linearization, parallelization. MOST operates within the Matlab/Simulink environment using the Simscape Multibody dynamics solver and leverages WEC-Sim, an open-source software for wave energy converter simulation, for hydrodynamics. A key advantage of MOST is its ability to reduce computational time compared to established codes such as OpenFAST. This is achieved through the simplification of aerodynamic computation and the use of pre-processed look-up tables for aerodynamic and mooring loads. The paper presents a comparative analysis between MOST and OpenFAST, an established open-source code widely used in academic research. The comparison is conducted using a case study involving a 15 MW reference wind turbine. The platform chosen instead is VoltturnUS-S. There were simulated through ten metocean conditions. The outcomes of the Reference point positions (RPP) in 6 d.o.f and the other relevant quantities, were analyzed computing a normalized root mean square error (NRMSE). Results demonstrate a favorable agreement between the two codes, with MOST showcasing a reduction in simulation time (up to 4 times faster than OpenFAST) while maintaining accuracy (overall mean of NRMSE almost 4%). This research significantly contributes to advancing simulation capabilities for offshore floating wind turbines, addressing critical challenges in the offshore renewable energy sector. MOST emerges as a powerful tool for researchers and engineers involved in offshore wind energy projects, offering a robust platform for simulating and analyzing complex systems in offshore environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

The analysis of offshore wind turbines relies on sophisticated simulation codes that integrate aerodynamics, hydrodynamics, structural mechanics, and control systems. These advanced tools simulate the dynamic behaviour of the turbine under various environmental conditions, accounting for interactions between components and external forces. However, ensuring the accuracy of these simulations requires rigorous verification and validation processes. Limited availability of real-world measurement data poses challenges to validating these simulation tools. These led to researchers in the field of offshore wind to relay their numerical model code to be verified as preliminary stage with a code-to-code comparison generally against benchmark code as OpenFAST (Jonkman

& Jonkman 2016) and OrcaFlex (Orcina: Ulverston) software. The work done in the paper Papi et al. (2024), aims to analyse the influence of modelling fidelity on the loads experienced by Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) substructures. It provides a comparative analysis of three FOWT simulation codes (Compare three FOWT simulation codes QBlade-Ocean, OpenFAST, and DeepLines Wind) in realistic environmental conditions. The study also evaluates the balance between computational time and accuracy of modelling theories for design load predictions in FOWTs. Or in the paper where the authors discuss the challenges in modelling Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) due to the strong coupling between the aerodynamics of the turbine Otter et al. (2022) and the hydrodynamics of the floating platform. It highlights the need for

high-fidelity numerical modelling as a substitute for physical testing, but also acknowledges the limitations of current numerical engineering tools. In Chen et al. (2022) proposes a coupling strategy between OpenFAST and WEC-Sim to provide a general solution for the design of offshore floating wind turbines (FOWTs). The study implements a fully coupled calculation by transferring the tower-base loads from OpenFAST to WEC-Sim, and in turn, platform displacements, velocities, and accelerations are transferred back. The paper validates this model based on the IEA-15-MW reference wind turbine and UMaine VoltturnUS-S semisubmersible platform. In the work Sirigu et al. (2022) were the first attempt to cross verification of the numerical model tool of MOST MORElab (2023) which is the in-house code developed at Politecnico di Torino and with the collaboration of the NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory) Leon et al. (2024). The following paper want to investigate and demonstrate the capability of the MOST tool comparing the results obtained against OpenFAST (Jonkman & Jonkman 2016) of simulating a FOWT platform as VoltturnUS-S with 15 MW NREL reference wind turbine Allen et al. (2020). The following paper is divided into the following section: materials and method section where the capabilities of MOST are displayed, setup of the comparison code to code, and results and discussion section.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

The MOST tool is developed in the WEC-Sim Tom (2014) environment, an open-source Matlab-Simulink software developed by the NREL.

It offers the ability to perform simulations of a complete FOWT system and also advanced configurations such as multibody simulation (taking into account hydrodynamic interaction) for cases with multiple floating wind turbines Figure 1, hybrid wind-wave platforms or floating pendulum-stabilized platforms, as well as being able to deal with platforms on which there are multiple turbines. MOST tool is user friendly indeed as display in Figure 2 representing the layout of two FOWTs Simulink model constructed with: mooring system, floating bodies, and the turbine blocks.

Figure 1: Systems that can be implemented with MOST (a: fixed platform, b: single FOWT, c: many turbines on the same floating platform, d: pendulum-stabilized FOWT, e: multiple FOWTs, f: Hybrid platforms

Figure 2: Simulink model of MOST

In MOST, the hydrostatic and hydrodynamic data required for simulation within WEC-Sim (the hydrodynamic problem is handled by blocks of the WEC-Sim library) can be easily created through the integrated use of the open-source tools SALOME (Électricité de France 2023) and NEMOH (Kurnia & Ducrozet 2022). Moorings can be modeled (by simply providing the main system characteristics as input) in several ways, with a linear model (providing stiffness and damping matrices), with a quasi-static nonlinear model, with look-up tables based on the latter, and through the use of the MoorDyn Hall (2020) tool that solves a lumped-mass problem. As for wind turbine data, such as geometric and inertial characteristics, control characteristics, and data for solving the aerodynamic problem, again these can be obtained by simple input of the main characteristics of the system during the pre-processing phase.

The wind turbine system Simulink model comprises rigid bodies representing the wind turbine components interconnected via fixed or revolute joints (Isoglio 2023) to consider inertial and gravity forces.

As for control actions, a dedicated subsystem deals with the calculation of generator torque and collective blade pitch angle (the user can choose between two control logics: ROSCO or Baseline (Issoglio 2023)). The aerodynamic forces acting at the root of the blades are calculated in a dedicated subsystem that takes as input the wind field and the motion of the degrees of freedom of the structure. The user can choose between two methods for calculating the aerodynamic forces:

- **MOST-BEM:** it is the configuration in which the aerodynamic load is computed at each iteration solving the BEM problem at each blade (refer into the paper Ning (2014)). That configuration is suggested to be performed if the user is looking into the driven dynamic quality reliability, but the time computation are higher.
- **MOST-LUT:** it is the configuration by which aerodynamic loads are calculated using look-up tables (having as input the effective wind speed, counting system motion, rotor angular velocity and blade pitch angle, and as output forces and torques at the root of each blade) obtained during a pre-processing phase (Figure 3). That kind of simulation are preferred when the primary user goal is to fasten the time computation with a medium-low quality in the dynamic's response meanwhile with a power output computation strongly reliable.

Figure 3: Look-up tables graphical example (inputs: Rotor speed, Blade pitch, Relative wind speed; outputs: aerodynamic forces and torques at blades root. In the image the torque along x-axis, T_x , is represented

2.1 Set-up simulation comparison MOST vs OpenFAST

In this paper, a three-bladed IEA-15-MW-RWT Gaertner et al. (2020) and UMaine VoltturnUS-S semisubmersible platform Allen et al. (2020), developed collaboratively by NREL, DTU and UMaine, is chosen as the validation model. The wind turbine has a rotor diameter of 240 m and a hub height of 150 m

above the still water level (SWL). The steel semisubmersible platform designed to support the IEA-15-MW wind turbine is moored with three catenary lines, with the anchors locating at a water depth of 200 m below SWL and at a radius of 837.6 m from the platform centerline. The case study environmental load was taken off through a site metocean analysis performed at Est cost of Ireland next to Dublin. A list of triplets representing the H_s , T_p and V_0 were extracted as done in the work Petracca et al. (2022) and were applied to the comparison analysis.

OpenFAST and MOST comparison have been done for firstly performing two kinds of simulation:

- Free Decay test;
- Operational sea state simulation with representative metocean triplets which serve as inputs of the comparison of OpenFAST against two modes discerning the aerodynamic computation interpretation as MOST-LUT and MOST-BEM;

To obtain a comparable result the following step has been set:

- OpenFAST input simulation does not account for the elasticity of the blade, primarily due to the rigid body nature of the MOST model.
- The hydrodynamic coefficients have been extrapolated identically for both simulations, facilitating a direct comparison, utilizing Nemoh (Kurnia & Ducrozet 2022).
- The OpenFAST simulation was conducted within a SIMULINK model, ensuring consistency in the control strategy for the wind turbine between simulations.
- The mooring in MOST is used the quasi-static nonlinear (Issoglio 2023); meanwhile OpenFAST use MAP++ Masciola et al. (2013)
- The wave elevations are obtained, for OpenFAST, by providing as input the JONSWAP spectrum characteristics (H_s and T_p) after which the wave elevation in time domain obtained as output from OpenFAST is provided as input in the MOST simulation.
- The simulation time runs for 1200 seconds and was performed on a PC with an Intel® Core™ i7-9700K CPU @ 3.60 GHz.

The comparisons of the free decay test have as results the reference point positions (RPP) where reference point means the projection of the center of the tower at the height of the SWL in 6 d.o.f. with the following initial conditions: surge=25 m, sway=5 m, heave=8 m, roll=8 deg, pitch=15 deg, yaw=5 deg. The simulation in operation mode shows the comparison in 6 d.o.f. reference displacement and rotor speed, power,

Figure 4: Comparison between MOST and OpenFAST free decay test results: 6 d.o.f. reference point displacements with the following initial conditions: surge=25 m, sway=5 m, heave=8 m, roll=8 deg, pitch=15 deg, yaw=5 deg

aerodynamic thrust and torque at hub reference frame and bending torques at tower base performed through the eleven representative triplets considering a turbulent wind irregular wave with JONSWAP spectrum with these characteristics. An error analysis based on a normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) is conducted to thoroughly evaluate the differences between MOST and OpenFAST.

The abovementioned NRMSE is defined in Eq. 1 as:

$$\text{NRMSE} = \frac{1}{y_n} \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m (y_k - y_{k,r})^2} \quad (1)$$

where $y_n = \max_k |y_r|$, r denotes reference values (OpenFAST results in this case), n stand for normalizing values, and m correspond to the length of the time series vectors. Regarding the computational time, were compared for each triplets the computational time enhancing a more complete comparison between the softwares.

3 RESULTS

In the following section, the results of the comparison of the case study presented in the previous section are summarized. Free decay test results are shown Figure 4. Due to the nature of the free decay test without wind-induced forces affecting the dynamics, the plotted data represent a unique version of MOST results. Additionally, in Figure 4, the results of the free decay test are displayed, considering turbulent wind and irregular waves with a JONSWAP spectrum, with the following characteristics: $H_s = 3.04$, $T_p = 10.48$ s, $V_0 = 11$ m/s). Figure 5 presents the results of the RPP in 6 degrees of freedom of the operational sea

state test, with results from OpenFAST, MOST-LUT, and MOST-BEM outputs depicted using solid black, yellow, and green colors, respectively. Figure 6 showcases the comparison of aerodynamic performances, including rotor speed, power, aerodynamic thrust, and torque at the hub reference frame, along with bending torques at the tower base. The color representation remains consistent across the three outputs. Table 3 summarizes the main insights of the error analysis based on the NRMSE. The lower bar houses the legends: in green denotes the value from the comparison between OpenFAST and MOST-BEM, while the yellow-sand color legend refers to the comparison between OpenFAST and MOST-LUT; in the grey cells are reported the relative max value of the correspondent feature obtained with OpenFAST. The left side of the Table indexes the features compared. The description of the metocean state is resumed in the bottom part of the table, reporting the V_0 , H_S and T_p . Table 4 collects the results (in seconds) of the computational time single performed for each triplet enumerated in ascending order of the wind speed, on the brackets there are the percentage value respect to the OpenFAST required time.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the present work is to introduce MOST tool and to validate it with a code-to-code comparison against the benchmark software OpenFAST. The section resumes the main insights of the results obtained as the correctness of the dynamics response framework:

- Free decay tests: in Figure 4 show that the RPP 6 d.o.f. has a comparable result, with a slight difference in amplitudes but on the other hand having good correspondence on oscillation periods

Figure 5: Comparison between MOST LUT, MOST BEM and OpenFAST 6 d.o.f. RPP. Common inputs are turbulent wind (mean wind speed $V_0 = 11$ m/s) and irregular waves (JONSWAP spectrum with H_s 3.04 m and T_p 10.48 s)

Figure 6: Comparison between MOST LUT, MOST BEM and OpenFAST rotor speed, power, thrust and torque at hub reference frame and bending torques at tower base. Common inputs are turbulent wind (mean wind speed $V_0 = 11$ m/s) and irregular sea state (JONSWAP spectrum with H_s 3.04 m and T_p 10.48 s)

- RPP in 6 d.o.f. comparisons referring to the Figure 5, show a better similarity between OpenFAST results against the MOST-BEM, due the more accurate aerodynamic solving methodology, meanwhile the MOST-LUT have some discrepancy in amplitude, but the trend is strongly attached to the OpenFAST reference. Referring to the Table 3 the quantitative comparison error analysis, MOST-LUT generally show a worst output in terms of NRMS, the higher value (0.27) is relative about the Roll rotation. The reasons can be traced to the nature of the aerodynamic force calculation method since the wind speed components along sway and heave are neglected and the wind speed along surge is averaged across the blade nodes to obtain a single relative wind input for the look-up tables. Nevertheless, in absolute term the comparison can be considered acceptable. Regarding the degrees of freedom surge, heave, and pitch, the results of the

error analysis are good

- Regarding the overall aerodynamic loads (Rotor Thrust and Torque) the results (Table 3), can be considered acceptable. The better instead is the comparison of the Power (NRMSE always lower than 2%) showing in both cases (LUT and BEM) wind turbines performances evaluations will be accurate.
- In Table 2 the comparisons highlights the better performance in time simulation. MOST -LUT computational time is up to 4 times faster than OpenFAST and MOST-BEM on average takes 60% the time that OpenFAST requires. Regarding computation times, it is noted that in generally MOST takes less time than OpenFAST does, especially for the case with look-up tables. On the other hand, attention is brought back to the fact that in one case MOST-BEM employs more

Comparison MOST-OpenFAST Results: NRMS Values

Surge	0.024	0.022	0.021	0.017	0.015	0.013	0.018	0.013	0.024	0.017	0.031	0.025	0.029	0.025	0.036	0.035	0.049	0.043	0.065	0.057
	15.7 m		18.3 m		24.2 m		27.2 m		25.9 m		22.5 m		21.5 m		19.4 m		15.9 m		14.9 m	
Sway	0.066	0.061	0.073	0.053	0.077	0.024	0.070	0.042	0.050	0.044	0.049	0.038	0.056	0.024	0.062	0.028	0.069	0.034	0.116	0.051
	1.69 m		1.84 m		3.09 m		4.25 m		4.24 m		4.4 m		5 m		4.71 m		4.59 m		4.53 m	
Heave	0.034	0.033	0.035	0.034	0.034	0.035	0.047	0.041	0.030	0.029	0.029	0.025	0.030	0.026	0.036	0.031	0.029	0.021	0.036	0.028
	0.705 m		0.724 m		0.808 m		0.825 m		0.902 m		0.916 m		1.02 m		1.13 m		1.38 m		1.5 m	
Roll	0.155	0.083	0.164	0.091	0.175	0.117	0.257	0.212	0.270	0.146	0.131	0.056	0.219	0.074	0.246	0.082	0.250	0.052	0.226	0.064
	0.469 deg		1.1 deg		1.28 deg		1.75 deg		1.82 deg		1.89 deg		2.38 deg		2.46 deg		2.55 deg		2.7 deg	
Pitch	0.018	0.011	0.018	0.011	0.017	0.010	0.052	0.016	0.087	0.065	0.039	0.020	0.050	0.023	0.038	0.020	0.037	0.012	0.042	0.011
	2.81 deg		3.54 deg		4.92 deg		6.93 deg		6.4 deg		5.71 deg		5.16 deg		5.88 deg		7.05 deg		7.72 deg	
Yaw	0.102	0.041	0.118	0.033	0.105	0.035	0.096	0.028	0.071	0.022	0.075	0.016	0.121	0.021	0.149	0.021	0.179	0.020	0.205	0.021
	2.45 deg		3.24 deg		4.21 deg		5.52 deg		7.34 deg		8.18 deg		6.7 deg		7.21 deg		8.03 deg		8.6 deg	
Rotor Speed	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.002	0.004	0.003	0.011	0.006	0.016	0.014	0.010	0.009	0.012	0.009	0.012	0.014	0.008	0.005	0.008	0.005
	7.61 rpm		7.68 rpm		8.07 rpm		8.48 rpm		9.05 rpm		9.74 rpm		10.9 rpm		11.7 rpm		12.9 rpm		13.7 rpm	
Power	0.007	0.006	0.010	0.006	0.017	0.010	0.019	0.010	0.019	0.015	0.013	0.012	0.015	0.013	0.017	0.019	0.011	0.007	0.012	0.007
	12.8 MW		13.2 MW		13.9 MW		15.9 MW		16.1 MW		15.9 MW		16.2 MW		17 MW		18.7 MW		19.8 MW	
Rotor Thrust	0.021	0.016	0.020	0.014	0.020	0.016	0.068	0.050	0.136	0.132	0.093	0.089	0.076	0.060	0.056	0.066	0.033	0.023	0.029	0.020
	1.27e+03 kN		1.58e+03 kN		2.26e+03 kN		2.66e+03 kN		3.12e+03 kN		3.79e+03 kN		4.68e+03 kN		5.55e+03 kN		6.81e+03 kN		7.69e+03 kN	
Rotor Torque	0.036	0.028	0.036	0.026	0.039	0.033	0.083	0.067	0.147	0.143	0.122	0.121	0.091	0.072	0.070	0.084	0.053	0.041	0.051	0.041
	9.4e+03 kNm		1.65e+04 kNm		2.36e+04 kNm		3.42e+04 kNm		4.27e+04 kNm		4.72e+04 kNm		6.97e+04 kNm		8.93e+04 kNm		9.75e+04 kNm		1.06e+05 kNm	
Tower Base T_x	0.135	0.072	0.142	0.079	0.148	0.099	0.244	0.200	0.238	0.132	0.132	0.060	0.194	0.066	0.214	0.072	0.214	0.046	0.193	0.055
	3.04e+04 kNm		7.14e+04 kNm		8.53e+04 kNm		1.04e+05 kNm		1.15e+05 kNm		1.05e+05 kNm		1.51e+05 kNm		1.6e+05 kNm		1.68e+05 kNm		1.8e+05 kNm	
Tower Base T_y	0.019	0.013	0.017	0.011	0.015	0.010	0.042	0.018	0.081	0.067	0.053	0.044	0.064	0.044	0.061	0.059	0.048	0.027	0.049	0.023
	1.94e+05 kNm		2.62e+05 kNm		3.94e+05 kNm		5.69e+05 kNm		4.9e+05 kNm		4.32e+05 kNm		3.69e+05 kNm		3.29e+05 kNm		4.13e+05 kNm		4.78e+05 kNm	
V (m/s)	5		7		9		11		13		15		17		19		21		23	
Hs (m)	2.66		2.62		2.79		3.04		3.39		3.69		4.18		4.64		5.37		5.8	
Tp (s)	10.59		10.54		10.59		10.48		10.46		10.40		10.37		10.29		10.83		10.54	
LEGEND																				
MOST LUT							MOST BEM							NORMALIZING VALUES (y_n)						
0 Max							0 Max													

Table 1 Comparison MOST-OpenFAST results: NRMSE errors values of some MOST-LUT/OpenFAST and MOST-BEM/OpenFAST relevant quantities time series with several environmental inputs combinations

time than OpenFAST, this happens because during such a test conditions are reached for which the relative wind-blade velocity is so low as to have inflow angles for which the convergence times of MOST's algorithm solving the BEM problem are definitely high.

Finlay, the mean overall NRMSE across the RPP and the aerodynamic features is almost 4% confirming the accuracy of MOST.

4.1 Further Implementation

In addition to the existing features, the potential for further enhancements and implementations in MOST is notable. The comparison outcome has provided valuable insights into mapping errors. Consequently, in the upcoming version, corrective measures will be implemented to address the primary discrepancies. For instance, enhancements will involve remodeling the LUT to incorporate not only the wind speed in the x-direction but also in the y-direction. This refinement aims to improve the accuracy of the simulation results and minimize discrepancies between the models. Future versions are anticipated to incorporate the integration of VAWTs (Vertical Axis Wind Turbines) into the model. Additionally, plans include the introduction of features for wind farm computation, integrating the code as an example with open source Pywake (?) software for wake modelling. Moreover, there are intentions to integrate capabilities for shared mooring design and structural analysis, thereby offering a comprehensive platform for offshore wind energy projects.

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Simulation Time Comparison (Simulated time: 1200 s)			
Triplet	OpenFAST	MOST-LUT	MOST-BEM
1	480.7 s	140.3 s (29.2 %)	561.5 s (116.8 %)
2	484.7 s	123.9 s (25.6 %)	303.9 s (62.7 %)
3	480.9 s	124.6 s (25.9 %)	284.3 s (59.1 %)
4	471.3 s	123.9 s (26.3 %)	279.5 s (59.3 %)
5	474.5 s	123.9 s (26.1 %)	277.5 s (58.5 %)
6	471.4 s	123.6 s (26.2 %)	277.1 s (58.8 %)
7	475.5 s	123.2 s (25.9 %)	280.2 s (58.9 %)
8	472.2 s	123.3 s (26.1 %)	286.2 s (60.6 %)
9	471.4 s	123.5 s (26.2 %)	292.3 s (62 %)
10	471.4 s	123.5 s (26.2 %)	300.2 s (63.7 %)

Table 2 Simulation time comparison

REFERENCES

- Allen, C., A. Viscelli, H. Dagher, A. Goupee, E. Gaertner, N. Abbas, M. Hall, & G. Barter (2020, 7). Definition of the umaine voltumnus-s reference platform developed for the iea wind 15-megawatt offshore reference wind turbine. *OSTI* 1(1).
- Chen, Z., Y. Jiarui, J. Sun, M. Tan, S. Yang, Y. Ying, P. Qian, D. Zhang, & Y. Si (2022, 07). Load reduction of semi-submersible floating wind turbines by integrating heaving-type wave energy converters with bang-bang control. *Frontiers in Energy Research* 10, 929307.
- Gaertner, E., J. Rinker, L. Sethuraman, F. Zahle, B. Anderson, G. E. Barter, N. J. Abbas, F. Meng, P. Bortolotti, W. Skrzypinski, G. N. Scott, R. Feil, H. Bredmose, K. Dykes, M. Shields, C. Allen, & A. Viselli (2020, 3). Iea wind tcp task 37: Definition of the iea 15-megawatt offshore reference wind turbine. *I*(1).
- Hall, M. (2020, 12). Moordyn v2: New capabilities in mooring system components and load cases. *I*(1).
- Issoglio, D. (2023). Most manual. Accessed on April 3, 2024.
- Jonkman, J. M. & B. J. Jonkman (2016, sep). Fast modularization framework for wind turbine simulation: full-system linearization. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 753(8), 082010.
- Kurnia, R. & G. Ducrozet (2022, 12). Nemoh v3.0 user manual.
- Leon, J., J. Grasberger, D. Forbush, M. Sirigu, M. Ancellin, N. Tom, A. Keester, K. Ruehl, D. Ogden, & S. Husain (2024, 1). Advanced features and recent developments in the wec-sim open-source design tool: Preprint. *Conference paper* 2(2).
- Masciola, M. D., J. Jonkman, & A. Robertson (2013, 1). Implementation of a multisegmented, quasi-static cable model. *I*(1).
- MORElab (2023). Most github page. Accessed on April 1, 2024.
- Ning, S. A. (2014). A simple solution method for the blade element momentum equations with guaranteed convergence. *Wind Energy* 17(9), 1327–1345.
- Orcina: Ulverston, U. Orcaflex.
- Otter, A., J. Murphy, V. Pakrashi, A. Robertson, & C. Desmond (2022). A review of modelling techniques for floating offshore wind turbines. *Wind Energy* 25(5), 831–857.
- Papi, F., G. Troise, R. Behrens de Luna, J. Saverin, S. Perez-Becker, D. Marten, M.-L. Ducasse, & A. Bianchini (2024). Quantifying the impact of modeling fidelity on different substructure concepts – part 2: Code-to-code comparison in realistic environmental conditions. *Wind Energy Science* 9(4), 981–1004.
- Petracca, E., E. Faraggiana, A. Ghigo, M. Sirigu, G. Bracco, & G. Mattiazzo (2022). Design and techno-economic analysis of a novel hybrid offshore wind and wave energy system. *Energies* 15(8).
- Sirigu, M., E. Faraggiana, A. Ghigo, & G. Bracco (2022, apr). Development of most, a fast simulation model for optimisation of floating offshore wind turbines in simscape multibody. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2257(1), 012003.
- Tom, K. R. M. L. Y.-H. Y. C. M. N. (2014, 11). Wec-sim (wave energy converter - simulator), version 00.
- Électricité de France (2023). Open source finite element code aster analysis of structures and thermomechanics for studies and research (version 16). Accessed on April 1, 2024.